

NAMES OF GEOGRAPHICAL PLACES RELATED TO PROFESSIONS IN SURKHANDARYA REGION

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ANNOTATION

This article talks in detail about the breads of the Surkhandarya region, a geographical place related to the profession, according to their origin. We will also study the specific features of these names, even the place names formed during the daily activities of the population. As you read this article, you will learn about several place names.

Key words: *profession, craftsman, farmer, pot, saddle, market, Kumkurgan, bow*

INTRODUCTION

An important factor in the naming of toponyms is the economic lifestyle, occupation, and economic activity of the people living in a certain area. This factor is little expressed in the place names of Uzbekistan, including the Surkhandarya region. Such place names are especially common in the microtoponymy of Sherabad, Denov and Boysun districts, where handicrafts have developed on a large scale.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the study of this article, the monograph "Geographic aspects of the study of toponyms of Surkhandarya region" by M.Kh Umarova, a senior teacher of Termiz State University, was widely used. This monograph contains excellent information about the origin, formation, and classification of toponyms in the Surkhandarya region.

The development of our national crafts, such as coppersmithing, blacksmithing, tailoring, and weaving, is little reflected in the toponymy of the regions. Many neighborhoods, neighborhoods, and streets are marked with words representing professions. Among these are such names as Jiyakchilik, Tarakchilik, Misgarlik, Postindoz, Chinnisoz, Egarchilik, Bakhmalbaf, Boyrabob, Boyrachi, Zhuvozzgar, Degrezlik.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Summarizing the names of places in this direction in Surkhandarya region, it is possible to divide them into groups according to the following professions:

a) place names associated with the names of metalworking craftsmen and the products they produce: such as Zargarguzar (Boysun district), Degrez (Oltinsoy district), Choyanchi (Sherabad district); There is a place called Zargarguzar Guzar in Boysun District. In this way, there was also a place where artisans and craftsmen live, who make jewelry from metal gold, silver, copper, etc.

The name of a village in Degrez-Sherabad District (Seplan), Altinsoy District. They were called degrez, i.e. pot pourers, because of their profession of melting pot and making household items and work tools such as pots, plow teeth, pans. Deg+rez in Persian-Tajik means deg-cauldron, rez-cast, i.e., the master of cast iron. In the sixties, the ancestors of most of the residents of this place were engaged in making agricultural and food items from cast iron, for example, plow teeth, hoes, shovels, shovels, as well as making cauldrons. There are many types of pots made by them, and they are known as doshkozon, kir pot, holwa pot, thai pot, two-eared pot, three-eared pot, tortukulli pot, chaksaki pot. In fact, the Degrezlik icon is composed of the Persian-Tajik verb deg-kazan, rez-rekhtan (to pour) in the present tense, and it means: "cauldron pourer".

The profession of potter or potter has existed in Uzbekistan since ancient times, and they made weapons of war, handicrafts, agricultural and household tools.

Craftsmen engaged in the craft of degrez used to live as a separate group, neighborhood. The place where they lived was named after this profession.

b) place names associated with the names of clay craftsmen and their products: such as Kulolon, Kololchi, Sopolli, Chinnisoz;

c) place names related to the names of crafts in the field of weaving and tailoring; Like Telpakchiyan (Sariosiyo district), Boyrabof (Kumgorgon district), Boyrachi (Denov, Sherabad district), Gilambof (Kiziriq district);

Boyrabab is a village in Kumgorgon district. Bob (bof) is the present tense form of the Persian verb baftan (to knit). Boyra is a tashama made of dense reeds and reeds of a certain length and tied with a thread (ribbon) in two or three places. Boyraposh means a weaver. The name of the village was created based on the profession of a group of people. Boyrachi-Denov is the name of a village in Sherabad district, and the name is based on the profession of boyra weavers.

g) place names related to the activities of craftsmen engaged in the profession of leather processing: Charmgar (Termiz), Charm guzar (Denov etc.); The name of the neighborhood in the cities of Charmgar-Termiz, Denov. This is the name of the neighborhood where a group of people lived in the 19th century engaged in leather processing, dyeing, and leather preparation. Charmgar is a miner, owner of a profession.

d) names of places related to the production of food products: Egarchi (Sherabad t), Egarchi-Sherabad district name of the village. A saddle is a wooden device that is put on a horse. Pronounced as edar in Old Turkic language. In Mahmud Kashgari's work "Devonu lugotit turk" -eyar-egar is written in song-egar style from the 14th century. Historically, it was a composite word, eg+ar, the base of the verb to bend, and the suffix -ar made a weapon noun. A saddler is a master saddle maker. The name of the place was named after the occupation of Guzar residents. The ancestors of the residents of the neighborhood called Egarchilik in the district were engaged in the work of making saddles, which were put on horses and adapted for riding. Saddles differed

from each other in their size, design, and material selection. The saddle is mainly made of hardwoods such as cypress, walnut, mulberry, and maple. Different patterns are drawn to make the saddles more attractive. Special attention was paid to the decoration of the saddle brow. The craft of saddlery has been handed down from generation to generation. That's why this neighborhood was called Egarchilik after its profession.

Place names related to agriculture are also found in the system of names of settlements. In the province

There are also villages such as Sariosiyo (Tegirmonboshi), Koshosiyoy (Koshtegirmon), Objuvoz, Zhuvozzgar, which are related to the name of local production enterprises that process agricultural products.

Lalmikor is the name of the population center of Kumkorgon district. In Persian-Tajik, it is made from the combination of lalmi and kor ozak. Depending on the type of farming and the method of using water, farming is divided into types such as semi-arid and semi-arid. Lalmikor is a method of growing agricultural products without using irrigation facilities (ditch, canal, dam) and with the help of natural soil moisture and rain. This settlement was established as a collective farm named "Lalmikor" in the 1940s, and after its expansion, it was preserved as a village name. Zhuvozzgar is the name of Guzar in Oltinsoy district. Juvozzgar is the driver and owner of this machine, and the person's profession was the basis for the name Guzar.

Objuvoz is the name of a place in Uzun district. Objuvoz is a water-powered device that makes the husk of rice suitable for consumption. The name of the village was called Objuvoz because it was built next to this production machine.

Tirgaron is the name of a village in Sariosia district. Persian-Tajik tir+gar+on. The word Tir has several meanings; - bow, crossbow, projectile; - home bolor, column; - Atorud sayere; -autumn season (Tiramo); -bièbon; - contribution, share. The affix -gar is a suffix that forms a noun of profession, and the affix -on indicates the plural. There were artisans who made Tirgaron bows, rifles, and their whites, and the name of the village came from their profession. Tirgaron also means carpenters.

Khoshman is the name of a village in Muzrabot district. As written in Tarikhi Narshakhi, brick-brick. The word "brick" in Sogdian is mein~mein-village, combined with the word "ovul", the variant "khisht+main>khishman>khoshman" is formed, meaning a village where bricks are made.

The importance of trade in the economic life of people in the region has been high since ancient times. Trade has influenced the prosperity of this area and the well-being of the population. That is why the term "market" is widely used in toponyms. Sometimes they gave names to the villages depending on the market day.

Toponyms in Surkhandarya region include Jumabozor, Chorshanbabozor, Payshanbabozor and Shanbabozor. Some place names consist of trade terms, such as Molbozor, Yilkibozor, Yangibozor, Bozormahalla, and the names of villages and neighborhoods were created in this way.

In the region, toponyms related to the phrase "market" may also be related to a person's name. An example of this is the name of the village of Handalbazor (Taipan) in Boysun district. The village was founded in 1975 by Handalbazor Eshkurbonov and was later named after him.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that when we study place names, their origin is related to various factors. The most important issue is to divide the current place names into groups and types. Geographical place names are very different - district, and some names are very strange. Their origins are also very different. It is also very difficult to classify them into species. It is often divided into types in terms of language rules. Above, we considered the influence of factors such as people's daily activities, profession, and craft on the emergence of place names in Surkhandarya region, the southernmost region of Uzbekistan. . We got information and knowledge about them.

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